

IUC 02: Framework for curation and distribution of reference datasets

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Materials science and engineering (MSE) research-related projects often rely on existing research data and knowledge as a baseline for generating new developments. However, some research data are scarce due to the particular experimental conditions at which they are acquired or the rarity of the material of interest. Moreover, the MSE field is broad and interdisciplinary, utilizing multiple research methods. This makes the related data highly heterogeneous, resulting in several different data formats and storage options. Besides that, the documentation of published MSE research results is often incomplete, so that e.g., experimental or simulation parameters and the data processing procedures are missing.

The factors mentioned above complicate the re-use of data, making the generation of new or enhancement of existing structure-property relationships challenging. Apart from being reusable, to adhere to the FAIR principles and carry out structured research data management (RDM), research data must also be findable, accessible, and interoperable. Achieving adherence to the FAIR principles is challenging and interdisciplinary, as RDM and MSE skills are required. Yet it is crucial to ensure that research data is trustworthy and can serve as a basis for generating new knowledge.

In this MSE context, reference data (RD) is, in principle, research data (experimentally generated or the result of simulations) that adhere to the FAIR principles and meet a very high-quality standard regarding documentation, measurement precision, and digital representation. Within [IUC02](#), we aim to develop a framework for the generation, distribution, and utilization of reference datasets (RDS), and we do it exemplary on the creep properties of a single crystal Ni-based superalloy. Our approach is highly interdisciplinary and considers the expertise and the requirements of RDM and MSE domain experts in the roles of data providers, data users, and infrastructure providers. Until now, no comparable framework or RDM concept has been systematically presented to the MSE community.

At the time of issuing this status report, we had achieved several milestones. The main milestone is the completion of a manuscript, which contains, among others, the description of the data handling

framework and related challenges. The proposed framework is technology-agnostic and comprehensively encompasses the steps needed to fulfill all the requirements for RD. It covers the entire data lifecycle, including data generation and documentation, dataset handling and storage, data shaping, sharing and publishing, data search and discovery, data retrieval, and data usage.

Moreover, the proposed framework considers an agreement on the mandatory content and its digital representation as FAIR Digital Objects, and the integration of RD into an easily accessible digital infrastructure for annotation, discovery, and dissemination of reference datasets using a data schema, an ontology, and a controlled vocabulary. The interplay between the digital representation with FAIR Digital Objects, the agreement on necessary metadata and related data schema, and an underlying ontology ensures that data can be efficiently accessed, shared, taken up, and re-used, thus fulfilling the FAIR principles.

Together with the submitted article, we published the first initial proposal of the definition for RD in MSE (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11667674>). Our proposal is an effort to address the lack of a community-agreed definition for RD in MSE domain. Furthermore, we published a first version of the data schema for creep data of Ni-based superalloys, including comprehensive documentation of test results and metadata (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11668376>). These two deliverables are integral to the framework development and can be further enhanced within the MSE community.

Further planned deliverables include the publication of a creep dataset on CMSX-6 (a single crystal Ni-based superalloy) in alignment with the data schema requirements and the hands-on implementation of the proposed framework, including as much as possible NFDI-MatWerk services. Both elements will serve as best-practice examples that demonstrate the applicability of the developed techniques. In this subsequent part of the project, we aim to publish further articles under the guidance of the respective leading project participants.

Creep data of Ni-based superalloys are well suited as an example for RD due to the high technical relevance, huge optimization potential of these materials, and the scarcity and often insufficient documentation of related published creep data. Furthermore, these materials have been well characterized by PP18 BAM and PP01 SFB/TR103 using a broad spectrum of characterization methods leaving in-depth data available. Still, we must remark that the proposed framework is applicable in general to research data and other materials and test types in the MSE field. Therefore, we believe it can have a substantial impact by supporting research, development, applications, and related collaboration within the MSE community. Therefore, we look forward to further community involvement and its implementation in other MSE areas.

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